

Abatement of 1,2,4 trichlorobenzene by ferrioxalate-mediated homogeneous photo-Fenton processes at near neutral pH using visible LED light: optimization by response surface methodology.

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Journal:

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The photo-Fenton degradation of a highly chlorinated aromatic solvent, 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene (124-TCB), for conditions of natural pH and using a Vis-LED as the radiation source is presented. A D-optimal design combined with response surface methodology (RSM) was combined to simultaneously evaluate the effect of the main reaction variables: hydrogen peroxide concentration (HP), iron dosage (Fe), and radiation level (Rad), on 124-TCB conversion. It was found that the photo-Fenton process is effective in the degradation of the chlorinated solvent employing a Vis-LED source when ferrioxalate is used as the catalyst source. Operating the system with high radiation levels ($I=0.15\text{Wcm}^{-2}$), the conversion of 124-TCB after 180 min of the reaction was higher than 75% over the full range of working HP and Fe concentrations. Being maximum ($X_{124\text{-TCB}}^{180} = 96.24\%$), the obtained for conditions of Fe=5 ppm and HP=305 ppm.

Introduction

There is significant environmental concern about chlorinated organic compounds (COCs) in wastewater, surface water, and groundwater due to their low biodegradability and high persistence. Under the EU Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC), several COCs (chloroethanes, chlorobenzenes, chlorophenols, dioxins, furans, chlorocyclohexane's, etc.) have been added in the last two decades to the list of substances to be monitored, encouraging limiting their production and use. However, due to their extensive use, these COCs still pose a risk for the water quality [1]. In this work, 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene (124-TCB) was selected as a model compound to study its abatement using the photo-Fenton process at neutral pH conditions using ferrioxalate as catalyst source, which was enhanced with visible monochromatic light-emitting diode (LED) light (470 nm). A D-optimal design combined with response surface methodology (RSM) was combined to simultaneously evaluate the effect of the main reaction variables: hydrogen peroxide concentration (HP), iron dosage (Fe), and radiation level (Rad), on 1,2,4-TCB conversion. Once the set of 15 experiments was performed (9 model points, 3 points to estimate the lack of fit, and 3 replicates to estimate pure error), the model was analysed by means of the analysis of variance. The largest effect was due to Rad, followed by Fe and finally the HP term. The evolution of the

chloride concentration (Cl^{-}) in the reactive medium was used as a direct measure of the level of detoxification (dechlorination) of 124-TCB and its chlorinated intermediates present in the system.

Material and Methods

The experiments were carried out in a cylindrical batch mixed reactor made of borosilicate glass, with an operating volume of 0.1 L. A jacket and a pumping bath of water were used to maintain a constant temperature in the reactor ($T=25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). The reaction mixture was illuminated with an LED lamp located at the top of the reactor (see Figure 1, Graphical Abstract). The light source was provided by a High-power collimated LED of Mightex (LCS-0470-50-11, Lasing, Spain). The LED emits at 470 nm with a clear aperture of 11 mm. The collimator light sources produce an optical power output of up to 4.17 W. The power could be adjusted using a Mightex BLS-13000-1E LED controller. The light LED source emits over a surface reaction of 11 cm^2 (reactor window). All irradiance measurements (I, Wcm^{-2}) were performed with a UV-VIS spectrometer FLAME UV-Vis coupled with an optical fibber.

To simulate the contaminated water, 124-TCB was added to a ferrioxalate solution prepared according to the Fe concentration to be used in the experimental test. The solution saturation was carried out under controlled temperature ($25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and 2 h of agitation; the 124-

TCB saturation concentration was 28 ppm (0.15 mM).

The organic compounds concentration in reaction samples were identified and quantified by Gas Chromatography (Agilent 6890N, Santa Clara, CA, USA) with a Mass Spectrometry Detector (GC/MS). Chromatography column HP-5MS (30 m × 0.25 mm ID × 0.25 μm) was used as a stationary phase and a constant flow rate of 1.7 mLmin⁻¹ of helium was used as a mobile phase. The chromatographic oven worked under a programmed-temperature gradient (starting temperature 80 °C, increasing the temperature at a rate of 18 °C min⁻¹ up to 180 °C, and then keeping it constant for 15 min). At this point, bicyclohexyl was used as a standard internal compound (ISTD) for the quantification of pollutants in reaction samples. The concentration of HP was determined by colorimetric titration, using a spectrophotometer at 410 nm (BOECO S-20 UV-VIS, Hamburg, Germany). Samples for iron determination were pre-treated with ascorbic acid, and the analysis was done by means of the colorimetric method with 1,10-phenanthroline at 510 nm. Ionic organic by-products, such as carboxylic acids and chlorides, were measured by Ion Chromatography (Metrohm 761 Compact IC, Gallen, Suiza) with anionic chemical suppression and a conductivity detector, using a SUPP5 5-250 column (25 cm length, 4 mm diameter) and an aqueous solution (0.7 mLmin⁻¹) of Na₂CO₃ (3.2 mM) and NaHCO₃ (1 mM) as mobile phase. The pH was measured with a Basic 20-CRISON pH (Barcelona, Spain) electrode. More details of the experimental device and the analytical techniques used can be found in Lorenzo et al., 2021 [2].

The collected sample (4mL) was filtered and extracted with 0.8 mL of n-hexane. The mixture of both phases was shaken for 2 min followed by 10 min of settlement, allowing the organic phase separation by decantation.

The key process parameters studied were HP concentration, between 61.50 and 612 ppm, Rad level, 0,1 (Low Rad) and 0.15 W cm⁻² (High Rad); and iron concentration, between 3 and 10 ppm. For all the operating conditions evaluated, an Oxalate/Fe molar ratio of 10 was adopted. This in order to prevent iron precipitation and maximize the fraction of radiation absorbed in the system [3].

The oxidant dose used varied from 0.5 (61.5 ppm) to 5 (612 ppm) times the stoichiometric amount, which was calculated assuming the complete mineralization of the initial concentration of 124-TCB (see Eq. 1).

The experimental design matrix obtained by D-optimal consisted in a total of 15 experiments. The 124-TCB conversion at 180 min of reaction ($X_{124-TCB}^{180}$) was

selected as the response under evaluation. The D-optimal design was selected due to its versatility to analyse categorical factors (Rad in this study).

Results and Discussion

RSM was performed to statistically evaluate the degradation of 124-TCB by a D-optimal design. Contaminant conversions after 180 min were fitted to a polynomial model. Multiple regression analysis was used to calculate the model coefficients and the analysis of variance (ANOVA) with a 95% confidence level. Satisfactory values of R² (0.986) and adjusted R² (0.979 and 0.9993, respectively) were obtained for the model. Eqs. 2 and 3 represent the RSM models in actual terms that describe the 124-TCB conversion for each Rad level studied (M1: Low Rad, M2: High Rad). Also, and from the ANOVA results, both models (M1 and M2) can be characterized as statistically significant.

$$X_{124-TCB}^{180}(M1) = 63.26 + 0.041 \cdot HP + 4.26 \cdot Fe - 0.000138 \cdot HP^2 \quad (Eq. 2)$$

$$X_{124-TCB}^{180}(M2) = 66.65 + 0.042 \cdot HP + 4.27 \cdot Fe - 0.000137 \cdot HP^2 \quad (Eq. 3)$$

From these equations, it can be observed that larger Fe and HP values (terms with a positive sign) would result in higher 124-TCB conversion. However, the concentration of the catalyst (Fe) being the term of greatest significance. On the other hand, the influence of the HP² term is negative since an excess of an oxidant agent produces a hydroxyl radical scavenging effect and accelerates its self-decomposition.

The response surface for M1 model is presented in Figure 2. First, note that for all the range of operating conditions studied, $X_{124-TCB}^{180}$ higher than 45% were obtained. The minimum value was obtained for conditions of HP = 612 ppm and Fe = 3 ppm. Here the inhibitory effect (free radical trapping) is observed when using high doses of oxidizing agent. On the other hand, the maximum $X_{124-TCB}^{180}$ was reached for conditions of medium/high dose of catalyst (7 / 10 ppm Fe) and low/medium doses of oxidant agent (61.5 / 350 ppm HP). Similar behaviour was obtained using high levels of radiation (I=0.15Wcm⁻²). However, the minimum $X_{124-TCB}^{180}$ obtained were higher than 75%. Therefore, it is worth noting the beneficial effect of radiation in the process.

Figure 2. Response surface for 124-TCB conversions after 180 min versus HP and Fe concentration. Low Rad Conditions ($I=0.1 \text{ Wcm}^{-2}$).

The concentration of chlorine atoms released by dechlorination of 124-TCB was measured for the different reaction times. The stoichiometric concentration of chloride was calculated using the experimental conversion of the pollutant at each reaction time and Eq. (4).

$$Cl_{stc}^t = C_{124-TCB}^{t=0} \cdot X_{124-TCB}^t \cdot \beta \cdot PM_{Cl} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

Where Cl_{stc}^t is the stoichiometric amount of chloride released to the aqueous phase (ppm); $C_{124-TCB}^{t=0}$ is the experimental initial concentration of the pollutant and $X_{124-TCB}^t$ is the experimental conversion of the contaminant at the different reaction times. In addition, β is the number of chlorines released (3, as is shown in Eq. (1), and PM_{Cl} is the molar weight of chlorine. Figure 3 shows the experimental and stoichiometric data of chloride concentration measured for conditions of maximum $X_{124-TCB}^{180}$ (High Rad, $HP=305 \text{ ppm}$ and $Fe=5 \text{ ppm}$). As can be seen, the experimental concentration of

chloride in the aqueous phase is lower than expected by stoichiometry.

Therefore, the total dechlorination of 124-TCB is not reached. These could be unidentified products or volatile chlorinated by-products, which could evaporate from the reaction media [4]. Thus, the higher conversion of 124-TCB is related to mild oxidant reaction conditions, promoting the fast mineralization of the chlorinated by-products, avoiding its volatilization from the reaction media. Here, it is important to note that it was only possible to obtain a better chloride balance (the difference between stoichiometric and experimental) for higher radiation doses. For conditions of $I = 0.22 \text{ Wcm}^{-2}$, and similar doses of oxidizing agent ($HP = 305 \text{ ppm}$) and catalyst ($Fe = 5 \text{ ppm}$) to those used in Fig. 3, after 180 min of reaction a difference between $Cl_{stc}^{t=180}$ and $Cl_{exp}^{t=180}$ of 1.3 ppm was obtained. It should be noted that the intensity of radiation used is 50% higher than that used in the conditions of Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Theoretical (orange) and experimental (blue) chlorides concentrations. High Rad conditions ($I=0.15 \text{ Wcm}^{-2}$; $HP=305 \text{ ppm}$; $Fe=5 \text{ ppm}$).

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Conclusions

124-TCB could be successfully degraded under photo-Fenton conditions at neutral pH using ferrioxalate and a Vis-LED as the iron and the radiation source, respectively. In order to study the effects of the process parameters: HP, Fe and Rad; a D-optimal experimental design combined with response surface methodology was applied. Among the studied variables, it could be seen that the largest effect in 124-TCB conversion was due to Rad (the most significant term), followed by Fe, and finally the HP term.

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HACE CONSTAR QUE:

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Presentaron la ponencia oral titulada:

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